

DESIGN CONSTRAINTS OF COMPOSITE LATTICE CYLINDERS FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS

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1 Introduction

Composite lattice structure is one of the promising concepts applicable to inter-tank, inter-stage or payload adapter structures of launch vehicles, major structure of spacecrafts, and structural components of non-pressurized sections of aerial vehicles. The competitiveness of the concept arises from the high structural efficiency which results in weight reduction from the conventional smeared, homogeneous structures. Applying filament winding or fiber placement techniques may also drastically reduce the fabrication cost of the lattice structures. The advantage of cylindrical lattice structure (Fig. 1) emerges especially under axial compression or bending, when buckling may be critical. From the manufacturing constraint, the ribs of the cylindrical lattice system comprise of hoop and counter-wound helical ribs, with the major load-bearing components under axial compression being the latter pair. The main role of hoop ribs is to sustain the helical ribs by carrying the hoop tension caused by resisting the circumferential component of compressive load conveyed by helical ribs.

The fundamental design methodology of lattice structures has been well described, for example by Vasiliev and Razin [1] and Totaro and Gurdal [2], with three independent constraints, *i.e.* (1) the strength of helical ribs, (2) the global stability of the cylinder, and (3) the local stability of the helical ribs. Recently, additional design constraint was assessed by Totaro [3] which dealt with the local buckling modes that are relevant to the series of multiple unit cells or repeated patterns of lattice system.

When considering the buckling of cylindrical shells, the design constraint may well be predicted to be the out-of-plane modes, which can be averted by increasing the shell bending stiffness. However, in the case of lattice cylinders, the compressive loads

generated in the helical ribs may also cause buckling with dominant in-plane displacements, which may be regarded as the distributed local rotational displacements in a macroscopic, homogeneous point of view. These modes of buckling usually do not appear in the cylindrical homogeneous shells. In the present study, design constraints of cylindrical lattice structure subjected to compressive loading is investigated, taking the effect of above local rotational displacements into account. The finite element parametric analyses are carried out in order to assess the effect of local rib displacements, including the apparent distribution of local rotations. Partial optimization of the structure is also addressed in the process of verification of the contention.

2 Design Constraints Identification

The well-known design constraints previously studied are insufficient as being discussed in the reference [3]. Buckling modes of lattice cylinders include those that are not categorized as either local or global in the sense of homogeneous smooth shells. These typical deformation modes essentially arise in association with the local rotational deformations of the ribs and rib intersections that cannot be described with the ordinary shell formulation. This may be taken into account in the regime of continuum mechanics using the higher order elasticity formulation such as the couple stress theory or the more general micropolar elasticity theory. However from the point of practical application, the behavior of the lattice cylinder is alternatively well pursued by the finite element analysis in which the ribs are modeled by the links of beam elements.

The lattice dimensions used hereafter are defined in Fig. 2. In order to first identify the dominating design constraints of the lattice cylinders, the simple

unit section of the lattice cylinder shown in Fig. 3 is examined. The effect of curvature of the unit cell on the deformation and strength behaviors are assumed to be small, and thus the component is fabricated in a flat configuration. Three types of specimens of different fabrication schemes are prepared (Table 1). The objective of the additional measures depicted in the table is that the intersection of the ribs placed in different directions are theoretically twice the thickness of that of the general region away from the intersection (Fig. 2). The resulting quality of the specimen without any specific treatment (Type A specimen) is shown in Fig. 4. The region adjacent to the intersection contains unacceptable amount of interlayer gaps. This was one of the biggest concerns in fabricating the lattice structure. The dimensions of the fabricated specimens varied according to the processes which are summarized in Table 2.

The mechanical behavior of the unit cell specimens under compressive loading was experimentally examined. The static compression experiments were thus conducted using the setup shown in Fig. 5. Both the top and the bottom ends of the specimens were immersed in the hollows of the aluminum blocks filled with the fusible alloy (melting temperature: 79°C) to achieve the fixed end conditions on the helical ribs. The ends of hoop ribs were kept unconstrained, which imposed weaker constraint than that in the actual lattice structure. The displacement versus load curves for specimens A, B and C are shown in Fig. 6. In all three specimens the local in-plane buckling of helical ribs first took place, which was followed by the decrease in apparent compressive stiffness of the specimens leading to the structural collapse. The loading was terminated after the flattening of load versus displacement curves occurred, except for specimen C, in which the compressive failure of helical rib took place at the portion close to the intersection. This was speculated to be due to the large local deformation induced after the buckling has occurred. The maximum compressive loads attained in each specimen are depicted in the figure.

The brief verification of the local buckling was also conducted based on the Euler buckling analysis which showed very good agreement with the experimental results. The buckling mode considered in the analysis was that of the clamped-simply supported beam, which simulated the span of the

helical rib between the helical-hoop ribs intersection and the helical-helical ribs intersection [2].

The outcome of these unit cell experiments is that the local buckling may possibly be critical in designing the lattice structure, or at least the buckling modes tied to the local rib rotations may be of significance and has to be included in the design constrains.

Fig. 1. Example of cylindrical lattice structure.

Fig. 2. Lattice dimensions.

Fig. 3. Unit cell specimen of lattice cylinder.

Table 1. Fabrication methods and materials of unit cell specimens.

Specimen type	Materials	Additional measures
A	CF/Epoxy Prepreg (Toho Tenax Q1111-2500)	--
B	CF Tow (Toho Tenax HTS40(12K) + Epoxy resin (Nagase Chemtechs XNRH6809)	Resin enriched
C	CF/Epoxy Prepreg (Toho Tenax Q1111-2500)	Prepreg patches placed between layers

Fig. 4. Through thickness view of intersection region obtained from X-ray CT (specimen A).

Table 2. Dimensions of unit cell specimens.

Specimen type	Helical rib width b_h [mm]	Hoop rib width b_c [mm]	Rib thickness H [mm]
A	2.8	4.5	10.4
B	3.6	4.8	10.3
C	4.1	4.9	10.5

Fig. 5. Compressive test configuration for unit cell specimen.

Fig. 6. Displacement vs. load curves of unit cell compressive test.

3 Buckling Analysis of Lattice Cylinders

3.1 Finite Element Modeling

The model cylinder considered in this study is identical to the cylindrical lattice component demonstrator of 2500mm in diameter and 2000mm in axial length designed by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) (Fig. 7). Its target buckling load is set to be 1500kN and the resulting total weight is 32.5kg. It consists of 71 pairs of helical ribs and 15 hoop ribs. FE model is created with 76680 beam elements and 73699 nodes each with 6 DOFs. To be as accurate as possible with the

use of beam elements, the intersection of two helical ribs is modeled with two series of beam elements placed sinusoidally and having offset to each other in the thickness direction at the intersection. This offset corresponds to the mid-plane misalignment of the two helical ribs. The inter-layer element is set up between the two intersecting rib elements to simulate the inter-layer resin, as shown in Fig. 8. The lattice dimensions defined in Fig. 3 have been intentionally varied in the following analyses to obtain the results under extreme cases.

Fig. 7. Demonstrator of cylindrical lattice component (by JAXA).

Fig. 8. Modeling of intersection of two helical ribs.

3.2 Effect of Local Rib Deformation

The Young's modulus is fixed here to be $E_h = E_c = 80\text{GPa}$ for both helical and hoop ribs to concentrate on the effect of lattice dimensions. The original JAXA demonstrator dimensions are first used to analyze the lowest buckling mode which is shown in Fig. 9. The major dimensions are shown in

the caption of the figure. This buckling mode has the circumferential wave number of 6 and the axial half-wave number is 5. This mode cannot be obtained from the unit cell analysis even with the use of periodic boundary conditions and thus the full model must be adopted. The buckling load is 636kN, which is 45% of the aimed 1500kN. The figure shows that the buckling mode comprises of the local rib rotational deformation which could not be taken into account in the preliminary design constraints [2].

The lattice dimensions are now altered to focus on the effect of local rotational deformations. The total weight has been kept constant, whereas the aspect ratio of the helical rib cross section H/b_h is increased to suppress the out-of plane deformation and alternatively induce the in-plane rotational deformations. As the original demonstrator exhibited shell-like buckling mode which embraced the out-of-plane deformations, this alteration can reduce the susceptibility against the out-of-plane mode. The buckling mode is shown in Fig.10 (a). The structure still exhibits a shell-like global buckling mode but with decreased amplitude. The in-plane rotation is yet distinguished. The buckling load is improved to 796kN.

To further sort out the effect of lateral rib rotations, the lattice dimensions are set so that the ratio of rib width is $b_c/b_h=3$, which makes the hoop rib well stiffer than the helical rib in in-plane bending. This is the value indicated in reference [3] as the recommended dimensions from the point of rib buckling. The lowest buckling mode is shown in Fig. 10 (b). The shell type buckling mode now disappears, and the local helical rib rotation distribution is apparent.

It is now clear that, (1) the local rotational deformation of the ribs may take place in the global buckling mode of lattice structure (Fig. 10 (a)), and (2) the local deformation of ribs may constitute the global buckling mode with locally distributed rotations (Fig. 10 (b)). It may thus be concluded that the local rotational deformation may play an important role in the formation of buckling modes. Morozov *et al.* [4] indicated that decreasing the number of helical ribs in the lattice results in the "frame-like" behavior, and the increase of that tends to approach the "shell-like" behavior. However, the local rotation of ribs may take place in any case, and the lack of consideration of this effect may be detrimental in designing the lattice structure.

Fig. 9. Buckling mode with original JAXA demonstrator dimensions, buckling load 636kN ($H=10\text{mm}$, $a_c=142.9\text{mm}$, $b_c=5.7\text{mm}$, $b_h=4.7\text{mm}$).

(a) Coupled global shell deformation and local rotational deformation, buckling load 796kN ($H=14.1\text{mm}$, $a_c=143.2\text{mm}$, $b_c=6.0\text{mm}$, $b_h=2.7\text{mm}$).

(b) Periodic local rotational deformation ($H=15\text{mm}$, $a_c=143.2\text{mm}$, $b_c=6.0\text{mm}$, $b_h=2.0\text{mm}$).

Fig. 10. Example of buckling modes with different levels of rib rotation effect.

3.3 Parametric Analysis of Buckling

The parametric calculation is conducted herein, in order to investigate the validity of the fundamental design methodology proposed in the reference [1]. The fundamental methodology employs the design constraints of helical rib strength and stability, together with the smeared global shell stability. This method is compared with the FE analysis adopted in the preceding sections.

3.3.1 Effect of Mesh Sparseness

There are five independent variables for a lattice cylinder with given cylinder diameter and length. For example, fixing the values of helical rib angle φ , rib thickness H , helical rib width b_h , hoop rib width b_c and number of helical rib pairs N_h results in the determination of lattice configuration. Now for a given case of fixed variables of weight, helical rib angle $\varphi=30^\circ$, helical rib cross section aspect ratio $H/b_h=2.13$, and the rib width ratio $b_c/b_h=1.2$ (these assumptions follow the JAXA demonstrator dimensions), setting a single parameter H will result in the fixation of the rest of the variables; b_h , b_c and N_h , together with already fixed φ . In this case, if H is set to be sufficiently large, then b_h is also fixed to a large value and the resulting N_h is a small value under constant weight, meaning that the lattice is sparse.

The consequence of the consideration is that the rib spacings a_h and a_c broaden as H increases. In the simplified methodology, global buckling has been treated by smearing the lattice into a homogeneous cylinder of equivalent average stiffness. According to this smearing procedure, equivalent membrane stiffness remains constant, whereas the equivalent bending stiffness increases with increasing H . Thus the resulting global buckling load increases along with the increase of H (Fig. 11, red line). Contrarily, the FE analysis with beam elements show that the buckling load of the lattice structure decreases with the increase of H (Fig. 11, blue line). This is due to the increasing susceptibility of local rotational deformation with increasing rib spacing. In other words, in this specific case, the “shell-like” lattice with decreased rib spacing or increased number of ribs may result in a favorable higher buckling load. This is contradictory to the result obtained by the smearing shell method. Thus the use of smearing method in the fundamental design methodology may

be misleading in certain cases as shown here. The use of analyses which can take into account the local behaviors of constituent ribs is preferable.

3.3.2 Effect of Rib Cross-Sectional Aspect Ratio

As it is challenging to fully conduct a design optimization of the lattice structure, another case study is given here under constant weight, rib angle φ , and number of helical rib pairs N_h . The parametric analysis is conducted to optimize the rib cross section aspect ratio H/b_h under the special condition of equal rib width $b_c/b_h=1$. As the weight is kept constant again in this case, and considering that the number of ribs is constant, the rib cross-sectional area is fixed. This results in the inverse proportional relationship between rib width $b=b_h=b_c$ and rib thickness H . Thus the buckling load analysis is conducted with varying H/b . As the result may be highly dependent on the rib cross-sectional area, *i.e.* the weight of the cylinder, the total weight is thus taken as a parameter. The resulting buckling load as a function of H/b is shown in Fig. 12. When $H/b < 0.4$, the buckling mode is apparently purely axisymmetric with out-of-plane shell deformation prevailing, and hoop ribs remaining undeformed (Fig. 13 (a)). At higher H/b , in contrast, the buckling mode shape becomes non-axisymmetric with in-plane rib rotation prevailing. The mode shape at $H/b > 5$ is shown in Fig. 13 (b). The initiation of decreasing tendency of buckling load at around $H/b = 5$ corresponds to this mode change due to the loss of in-plane bending stiffness of the ribs.

The result of Fig. 12 seems to be relatively independent to the value of rib cross-sectional area, or equivalently the cylinder weight in the present case. The maximum buckling load may be achieved at around $H/b = 5$ for any of the cases. This is in nature due to the mode change of the rib deformations, between out-of-plane and in-plane tendencies.

As the value of b_c/b_h is fixed to unity in this case, the optimized configuration of the lattice is not yet clear. Next step is to verify the effect of the relationship between the dimensions of helical and hoop rib cross sections. This process can also be treated similar to that shown in this part by taking b_c/b_h as a variable while setting H/b as a parameter.

Fig. 11. Effect of rib height on the buckling load under constant weight.

Fig. 12. Buckling load as a function of rib aspect ratio.

(a) Axisymmetric mode at low H/b .

(b) Non-axisymmetric mode at high H/b .

Fig. 13. Buckling modes at different H/b .

4 Effect of Skin Addition

The local deformation of ribs, especially the in-plane rotation, may significantly lower the buckling load of lattice cylinders as shown in the previous chapter. The possible improvements of the structure by adding a sufficiently thin skin is considered herein. The basic idea is to increase the resistance of ribs to the in-plane rotational deformations by efficiently reinforcing the ribs with thin skin through the exploitation of its shear and tensile rigidity. Though the consequent structure is topologically identical to the isogrid panel structure, the intrinsic idea is completely different in the essence that, for the isogrid, the skin is the primary component which is reinforced by the grid shaped stiffeners. In contrast,

for the present lattice with skin addition, the primary structural component is the lattice and the skin is used as to constrain the deformation of the lattice. The stiffeners in isogrid panels are mainly to increase the out-of-plane bending stiffness of the panel, whereas the skin for the lattice structure is to increase the local rigidity of ribs to suppress the in-plane deformation.

FE model is again constructed based on the previously used beam element model. The base lattice structure has dimensions of $\varphi=21.2^\circ$, $H=10\text{mm}$, $a_c=143.2\text{mm}$, $b_c=5.0\text{mm}$, $b_l=5.0\text{mm}$. The skin is modeled with the 4-node thin shell element. The skin elements are connected to the lattice beam elements at corresponding nodes, with rigid gap elements placed in the thickness (radial) direction of the cylinder to account for the thickness of the lattice beam and the skin (Fig. 14). In other words, the rigid gap element is placed to connect the node at the neutral line of the beam element and that at the neutral surface of the shell element. The base lattice model has reduced number of elements due to the limitation of computer memory, compared to the model in the previous chapter. The total number of nodes of the employed model with skin is 48849 compared to 73699 of the preceding pure lattice model.

The effect of adding the aluminum alloy skin on buckling is calculated as shown in Fig. 15. The base lattices cylinder has the buckling load of 660kN, which is almost identical using the finer mesh of the previous model and thus the model is presumably accurate. The addition of skin efficiently increases the buckling load especially at small skin thickness. With the skin of 0.1mm thickness, the buckling load more than doubles up to 1558kN. The buckling load of the pure cylindrical shell of the same dimension with 0.1mm-thick aluminum alloy, which by itself is not of practical use, is estimated to be mere 27kN. Thus the synergetic effect of the skin addition to the lattice cylinder is enormous.

The buckling mode shapes of the base and the amended lattice cylinders are shown in Fig. 16. The suppression of the rib local in-plane rotational deformation by the presence of skin is obvious.

The weight of the base lattice is estimated to be 32.5kg and the weight of the 0.1mm-thick skin is 4.4kg for the present configuration. This corresponds to the weight increase of 13% by the skin addition.

Fig. 14. Skin-added model of the lattice.

(a) Without skin addition (base model).

(a) With skin addition (skin thickness 0.1mm).

Fig. 15. Effect of skin addition on the buckling load of lattice cylinder.

Fig. 16. Effect of skin addition on the buckling mode.

5 Conclusions

The present study focuses on the effect of local rotation of the ribs on compressive buckling behaviors of lattice cylinders, which may not be embraced in the context of either the global buckling estimations combined with smearing method, or the simple local Euler buckling of the ribs. The use of beam elements in the finite element modeling may well be sufficient in order to include the effect of local rib rotational deformations in the lattice structure. The consequence of considering this effect may drastically lower the buckling load estimation compared to the combined methodology taking into account the conventional shell buckling, rib local Euler buckling and rib failure strength. Design constraints for lattice structure should certainly include the effect of rib local deformations. The addition of thin skin to the lattice structure is also proposed in order to prevent or reduce the infection

of this local deformation nature of the ribs. The present paper focuses on the cylindrical lattice structure under pure compressive loading, but similar behaviors affected by rib deformations are observed under lateral shear, bending and torsion, to which the addition of thin skin is also effective. The merit of installing the skin may also arise when the lattice structure is applied to the aircraft fuselage with cabin pressurization requirement.

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